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ARTISANAL PRODUCTION DURING THE REIGN OF AMIR TEMUR AMIR TEMUR DAVRIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK REMESLENNICHESTVO V ЭПОХУ АМИРА ТИМУРА

Badalbaeva Irodakhon Khabibulaevna,

Badalbayeva Irodaxon Xabibulayevna

Бадалбаева Иродахон Хабибулаевна

Andijon qishloq xo'jaligi va agrotexnologiyalar instituti "Gumanitar fanlar"
kafedrasi assistenti (PhD)

ассистент (PhD) кафедры «Гуманитарных наук» Андижанского
института сельского хозяйства и агротехнологий
assistant (PhD) of the department of "Humanities" Andijan Institute of Agriculture
and Agro-Technology

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Abstract: This article examines the issues of handicraft relations in the state of Amir Temur. On this basis, handicraft production, which was one of the most important spheres of economic life during the Timurid period, has been studied in the context of economic activity. The types of handicraft activities in the territories of the Timurid state are also considered from a regional perspective.

Keywords: handicraftsmanship, craftsmanship, brocade fabric, satin, crimson fabric, gold-woven brocade, trade, glassmaking, master, craftsman

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы ремесленных отношений в государстве Амира Темура. На этой основе исследовано ремесленничество как одна из важнейших сфер экономической жизни в период Темуридов при осуществлении хозяйственной деятельности. Также виды ремесленной деятельности на территориях государства Темуридов рассмотрены в региональном разрезе.

Ключевые слова: ремесленничество, парчовая ткань, атлас, багряная (красная) ткань, золототканая парча, торговля, стеклоделие, мастер

Some issues of craftsmanship and trade relations during the era of Amir Temur and the Timurid Empire were to a certain extent covered in the studies of Vasily Vladimirovich Bartold, A. A. Molchanov, S. A. Azimjonova, and N. Mahmudov.

According to the sources left by Ibn Arabshah, Amir Temur "gathered around himself thoughtful people, representatives of learning, intelligent and capable individuals, as well as skilled craftsmen and masters." He was a patron of science, culture, and trade, and provided comprehensive support for the revival of the traditions of the Silk Road. The prominent Russian historian and orientalist, academician Vasily Vladimirovich Bartold, who deeply studied the history of Central Asia, outlined the main stages of the life and activity of Amir Temur in the 1901 edition of the "Brokhaus-Efron" Encyclopedic Dictionary and evaluated both his conquering and constructive activities.

During the reign of Amir Temur, the development of craftsmanship contributed to strengthening the economic power of the state. Workshops in the cities served not only as economic centers but also as centers of culture. The progress of craftsmanship was closely

connected with the development of trade and commerce. The attention given to craftsmen by the Timurid Empire rulers also had a positive influence on the development of science and culture.

Amir Temur encouraged the economic activity of the population, which led to increased incomes, stronger purchasing power, and a desire to improve living conditions. As a result, the territory of Movaraunnakhr became almost entirely covered with cities, villages, and settlements. In the capital and major cities, active trade was conducted not only in local products but also in goods brought through the Silk Road. These included fur, leather, pottery products, spices, jewelry, cosmetics, medicinal herbs, and other goods. Trade in livestock and other animals was also well developed.

Amir Temur followed the advice of wise scholars and enriched the experience of state administration, while highly valuing enterprising and initiative-driven people. He stated: “My experience has shown that determined, proactive, vigilant, courageous, and fearless people are superior to indifferent and unenterprising individuals.” An experienced person provides work for thousands of people. “From my experience, I learned that victory is achieved through the help of Allah and the initiative of human beings.” These ideas have not lost their significance even today. “Temur Tuzuklari” is a treasury of wisdom, and every thought expressed in it carries profound meaning.

Local craftsmen produced leather and wool products of high quality. The markets were well supplied with dairy and meat products, and fish was also sold. As a result of the close economic cooperation between the urban and rural populations, as well as the harmonious development of craftsmanship, agriculture, and caravan trade, a distinctive economic potential was formed. This ensured the strength of the Timurid Empire and increased the welfare of the people. These three main sectors — urban craftsmanship, agriculture, and trade — complemented and supported one another.

The production of silk fabrics was highly developed, and these fabrics became luxury goods used by the upper classes and were also exported through foreign trade. The brocade fabrics, atlas silk, and crimson textiles of Samarkand, as well as the kimkhab fabrics of Herat, were especially famous. Wool products such as carpets, rugs, and other items were produced not only by urban craftsmen but also by nomadic pastoralists.

When speaking about the craftsmanship of Samarkand, special attention should be given to the paper production center located near the Obi-Rahmat canal. High-quality paper was produced there using advanced technology, and Samarkand paper became famous throughout the region and was considered an important export commodity.

In the XVth century, glassmaking was also highly developed, and various containers and household items were produced. Colored glass was used in house construction and decoration. Woodworking also occupied an important place, producing labor tools, carts, molds, chests, cradles, and other items. Leather production and the manufacture of leather goods were also widely developed. During preparations for military campaigns, quivers for arrows and sheaths for swords and knives were produced as well.

Thus, the rapid development of productive forces and the economy in Movaraunnakhr and Khorasan led to the expansion and centralization of production, improvements in quality, and the emergence of the first elements of manufacturing. For example, the textile enterprises known as “bayt al-tiriz,” which operated in Bukhara and Merv, represented a form of feudal cooperation by employing free hired workers, dependent peasants, and slaves, according to the accounts of Muhammad Narshakhi and Al-Utbi.

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